

Synthesis of Some Phenoxyacetyl Thiosemicarbazide Derivatives and Derived 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles

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Eleven 4-sec.-amyl phenoxyacetyl thiosemicarbazides have been synthesised as possible insecticidal agents by the condensation of 4-sec.-amyl-phenoxyacetyl hydrazide with arylisothiocyanate, five of them have been cyclized by iodine to 2-(4-sec.-amyl-phenoxy-methyl)-5-(substituted arylamino)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles. Some thiosemicarbazides have been screened for their anti-acetyl cholinesterase activity.

HYDRAZIDES have been associated with anthelmintic¹ and antifungal activity. Organosulphur compounds have been used widely as possible insecticides, fungicides and acaricides²⁻⁵. Fungicidal properties of phenyl thiosemicarbazide are well known. Thiosemicarbazides have been reported to possess good antitubercular⁶, antifungal⁷⁻⁹ and herbicidal activity¹⁰. Recently Sen Gupta *et al.* reported various thiosemicarbazides exhibiting anti-cholinesterase activity.¹¹ On cyclization these compounds yield substituted 1,3,4-oxadiazoles. The oxadiazole nucleus itself, has been associated with various pesticidal activities¹²⁻¹⁴. In view of these several thiosemicarbazides and oxadiazoles have been synthesized with a view to study their insecticidal and other biological properties.

In all eleven thiosemicarbazides and five oxadiazoles have been prepared according to the scheme given below :

Experimental

(All the m.p.s. are uncorrected).

4-sec.-amyl phenoxy acetyl hydrazide (I)

A mixture of 0.2 mole of 4-sec.-amyl phenol, 0.2 mole of chloroethylacetate and 0.2 mole of anhydrous potassium carbonate in 100 ml. of acetone was refluxed on water-bath under anhydrous condition for 12 hr, filtered and the excess of solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The residue, thus obtained, was treated with ethanol (50 ml). Hydrazine hydrate (99-100%) 0.2 mole was added to it and refluxed for 18 hr. The excess of ethanol and water was distilled off under reduced pressure. The crude product, which separated out on cooling in ice-bath, was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 102°. Yield 60%. Anal. Calcd. for C₁₃H₂₀N₂O₂; N, 11.86%. Found N, 11.72%.

4-sec.-amyl phenoxyacetyl thiosemicarbazide (II)

A mixture of 0.01 mole of 4-sec.-amylphenoxy acetyl hydrazide (I) and 0.01 mole of appropriate arylisothiocyanate in 30 ml. of ethanol was refluxed on steam-bath for 4 hr. The reaction mixture cooled in ice-bath and solid mass which separated out, was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. Yield 55-75% (Table 1).

2-Substituted amino-5-(4-sec.-amyl phenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (III)

Method of Paul and Basu¹⁵ was used. The appropriate thiosemicarbazide (II), 0.01 mole was suspended in ethanol (95%, 300 ml.). To this mixture NaOH (6N, 5 ml) was added with cooling and shaking. To this clear solution I₂ KI solution (5%) was added gradually with stirring till the colour of I₂ persisted at room temperature. The contents were heated under reflux on a water bath and more I₂

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	R	Mol. formula	M.P. °C	% of Nitrogen	
				Calcd.	Found
1.	Phenyl ^a	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	147	11.32	11.38
2.	2-Methyl phenyl	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	158	10.91	10.66
3.	3-Methyl phenyl	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	142	10.91	10.82
4.	4-Methyl phenyl ^b	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	144	10.91	10.78
5.	3-Chloro phenyl	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	145	10.36	10.42
6.	4-Chloro phenyl ^c	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	161	10.36	10.25
7.	4-Bromo phenyl ^d	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ BrN ₃ O ₂ S	155	9.33	9.45
8.	4-Iodo phenyl ^e	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ IN ₃ O ₂ S	152	8.45	8.17
9.	2-Methoxy phenyl	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ N ₃ O ₃ S	99	10.47	10.52
10.	1-Naphthyl	C ₂₄ H ₂₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	84	9.98	10.14
11.	2-Naphthyl	C ₂₄ H ₂₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	143	9.98	9.77
a.	i.r. absorption, CONHNH, 2900 and 3300 cm ⁻¹ ; Co, 1700 cm ⁻¹ ; CNH, 1550 cm ⁻¹ ; NHCS, 1360. cm ⁻¹ .				
b.	i.r. absorption, CONH, 2940 and 3250 cm ⁻¹ ; Co, 1700 cm ⁻¹ ; CNH, 1540 cm ⁻¹ ; NHCS, 1360 cm ⁻¹				
c.	i.r. absorption, CONHNH, 2900 and 3200 cm ⁻¹ ; Co, 1700 cm ⁻¹ ; CNH, 1550 cm ⁻¹ ; NHCS, 1365 cm ⁻¹ .				
d.	i.r. absorption, CONHNH, 2950 and 3240 cm ⁻¹ ; Co, 1700 cm ⁻¹ ; CNH, 1550 cm ⁻¹ ; NHCS 1365 cm ⁻¹ .				
e.	i.r. absorption, CONHNH, 2950 and 3250 cm ⁻¹ ; Co, 1700 cm ⁻¹ ; CNH, 1550 cm ⁻¹ ; NHCS, 1370 cm ⁻¹ .				

solution added carefully till the permanent tinge of excess I₂ remained. The reaction mixture poured into 500 g. of ice, and precipitated solid filtered, washed with water and CS₂. The crude product was crystallised from dilute ethanol (1 : 1). Yield 50-65% (Table 2).

TABLE 2

Sl. No.	R	Mol. formula	M.P. °C	% of Nitrogen	
				Calcd.	Found
1.	Phenyl ^a	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂	138	12.46	12.66
2.	4-Methyl phenyl ^b	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₂	113-5	11.96	12.12
3.	4-Chloro phenyl ^c	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ ClN ₃ O ₂	141	11.31	11.22
4.	4-Bromo phenyl ^d	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ BrN ₃ O ₂	135-7	10.09	10.24
5.	4-Iodo phenyl ^e	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ IN ₃ O ₂	138	9.07	9.16
a.	i.r. absorption, NH, 3360 cm ⁻¹ ; OCN, 1650 cm ⁻¹ ; NCN, 1585 cm ⁻¹ .				
b.	i.r. absorption, NH, 3340 cm ⁻¹ ; OCN, 1640 cm ⁻¹ ; NCN, 1580 cm ⁻¹ ;				
c.	i.r. absorption, NH, 3360 cm ⁻¹ ; OCN, 1640 cm ⁻¹ ; NCN, 1585 cm ⁻¹ .				
d.	i.r. absorption, NH, 3345 cm ⁻¹ ; OCN, 1640 cm ⁻¹ ; NCN, 1585 cm ⁻¹ .				
e.	i.r. absorption, NH, 3350 cm ⁻¹ ; OCN, 1650 cm ⁻¹ ; NCN, 1590 cm ⁻¹ .				

Enzyme preparation

Male adult albino rats weighing approximately 200-220 g. were killed by decapitation. Brains were quickly removed and homogenized in ice-cold 0.25M sucrose with the help of a Potter-Elvehjem type homogenizer fitted with a teflon pestle.

Determination of acetyl cholinesterase (AChE) activity

The method of Hestrin¹⁶ as described by Colwick and Kaplan¹⁷ was used. The reaction mixture in a

final volume of 1.5 ml. contained 0.075M phosphate buffer, pH 7.4, 4 mM acetyl choline and 0.2 ml of 10% (w/v) homogenate. The reaction mixture with or without test compounds was incubated in a constant temperature water bath for 5 min after which the reaction was started with the addition of acetyl choline. The reaction was stopped after 10 min. with the addition of 2 ml of alkaline hydroxylamine reagent (made by mixing equal volumes of 3.5N NaOH and 2M hydroxylamine within an hour of use). Immediately after the addition of hydroxylamine reagent, 1 ml of cold 4N HCl was added to precipitate the protein as well as to bring the pH sufficiently acidic (pH 1 to 2). After centrifugation (at 500 × g for 5 min) the supernatant was transferred into a separate tube. Colour was developed promptly by adding 1 ml of 0.37M ferric chloride in 0.1N HCl and the intensity of colour was measured at 540μ. All compounds were dissolved in propylene glycol (100%) and used at 3 × 10⁻⁴M. A control containing equal volume of propylene glycol was also run in parallel. Each assay was done in duplicate.

Result

Six compounds of the Table 1, namely 3, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 11 were tested. Unfortunately no compound showed activity except compound no. 6 which showed marginal inhibition (9.74%).

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